

1 *Supplementary material for*

2 **Liquid-liquid chromatography isolation of *Petasites hybridus* sesquiterpenes and their LC-**
3 **HR-MS/MS and NMR characterization.**

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88 **Fig. S1.** CPC online chromatogram

89 Data are presented as absorbance vs. separation time. Parameters: *n*-hexane/ethyl acetate/methanol/acetonitrile
 90 (5/1/5/1, v/v/v/v); descending (DSC) mode (lower phase as mobile phase); $V_{column} = 250$ mL; $\omega_{rot} = 1700$ rpm; $F = 10$
 91 mL/min; $V_{inj} = 10$ mL; $\lambda = 230$ nm; $S_F = 0.72$ (measured at the end of the experiment); the feed sample was prepared by
 92 dissolving the *P. hybridus* extract in the lower phase at a concentration of 40 mg/mL
 93

(e)

Petasin P5

(f)

Petasin P6

(g)

Petasin P1

(h)

Petasin P2

(i)

Petasin P3

(j)

Petasin P4

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Sel-TOCSY 6.07ppm 120ms – NS=256

116

117 **Fig. S12.** Selective-TOCSY NMR spectrum of compound P2 at 30° C in deuterated CH₃OD.

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119 **Fig. S13.** Selective-TOCSY NMR spectrum of compound P2 at 30° C in deuterated CH₃OD.

Sel-TOCSY 2.99ppm 120ms – NS=256

120

121 **Fig. S14.** Selective-TOCSY NMR spectrum of compound P2 at 30° C in deuterated CH_3OD .

Sel-TROESY 4.98ppm 250ms – NS=1024

124

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Sel-TROESY 2.99ppm 250ms – NS=1024

126

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Sel-TROESY 2.28ppm 250ms – NS=512

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13C DEPT Q – NS=2048

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137 **Fig. S22.** ^{13}C DEPTQ NMR spectrum of compound P3 at 30° C in deuterated CH_3OD .

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SeI-TOCSY 4.96ppm 120ms - NS=256

146

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SeI-TOCSY 2.12ppm 120ms - NS=256

150

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Sel-TOCSY 1.05ppm 120ms - NS=256

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Sel-TOCSY 0.83ppm 120ms - NS=256

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Sel-TOCSY 1.76ppm 120ms - NS=128

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Sel-TROESY 5.05ppm 250ms – NS=1024

176

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Sel-TROESY 3.14ppm 250ms – NS=1024

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193 **Fig. S50.** ^1H - ^{13}C HMBC NMR spectrum of compound P5 at 30° C in deuterated CH_3OD .

Arrayed Sel-TOCSY 4.99ppm – NS=128

194

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Sel-TOCSY 6.12ppm 120ms - NS=64

196

197 **Fig. S52.** Selective TOCSY NMR spectrum of compound P5 at 30° C in deuterated CH₃OD.

CSSF-*Sel*-TOCSY 3.03ppm 120ms – NS=256

198

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Sel-TOCSY 3.03ppm 120ms - NS=128

200

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Sel TOCSY 3.23ppm 120ms - NS=64

202

203 **Fig. S55.** Selective TOCSY NMR spectrum of compound P5 at 30° C in deuterated CH₃OD.

Sel-TROESY 5.01 250ms – NS=256

204

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Sel ROESY 3.23ppm 250ms - NS=256

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207 **Fig. S57.** Selective ROESY NMR spectrum of compound P5 at 30° C in deuterated CH_3OD .

1H NS16 MeOD 30C - 8 mg in 0.7 mL - NS=16

208

209 **Fig. S58.** ¹H NMR spectrum of compound P6 at 30° C in deuterated CH₃OD.

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Sel-TOCSY 6.13ppm 120ms – NS=128

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